

CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PVDF PIPE

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Keywords: *Carbon Fibre, Thermoplastic, Composite Pipe, Mechanical Strength*

1 General Introduction

Conventional high performance fibre reinforced polymer composites have outstanding mechanical properties, exhibiting high strength and stiffness combined with low weight and susceptibility to fatigue and corrosion. The use of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites is increasing in the recent years especially in applications where material cost is secondary to performance and weight reduction. Once dominating the aerospace applications, CFRP composites are now being considered as the key material for application in deep-sea oil and gas exploration. This is due to the remarkable properties and the tailorability of fibre reinforcement along load paths to achieve excellent composite performance, which is an attribute not found in any other material.

Over the past two decades, composite materials have progressed and are now being used in secondary structures on offshore oil platforms such as gratings, staircases, handrails, accommodation modules, high pressure tubing, fire water main and deluge pipes replacing metals [1]. Reduction in weight is directly translated in the savings of structural costs for construction of offshore platforms. It has been reported that weight savings of 50 to 70% are possible when using composites in offshore as compared to conventional steels [2]. In weight sensitive applications, such as Tension Leg Platforms (TLP), a weight reduction of a

component by 1 kg translates to 2 kg weight being removed from the rest of the structure [3].

When a composite is in service, it is the matrix that comes into contact with the environment that the material is exposed to. Matrix is the barrier of the composite, determines its inertness and acts as the protection for the reinforcing fibres. Primary characteristics for reinforcing fibres in inert composites are high stiffness and strength, in which carbon fibres outperform other fibres. Furthermore, such properties are unaffected in hostile environments such as elevated temperatures, exposure to common solvents and fluids, and environmental moisture which makes them chemically and mechanically favourable. Therefore, it is important to select the right matrix for the manufacture and characterisation of inert composites.

In this study, high strength and modulus carbon fibre was chosen as reinforcement in polyvinylidene fluoride, which is known to have an excellent toughness and corrosion resistance. This in turn gives a promising new material which is strong and durable. Polyvinylidene fluoride has excellent chemical resistance, low permeability to gases and liquids and low water absorption (0.03%), which are key for deep sea oil and gas applications. Furthermore, in the oil and gas industry, polyvinylidene fluoride has already been recognised and used as pipe liner especially when the material has to withstand highly corrosive fluids [4]. To exploit the full

benefits of polyvinylidene fluoride, it has been reinforced with carbon fibres [5-6]. The main aim here is to demonstrate that this novel material can be an alternative for offshore oil and gas applications. The ‘one material concept’ in composite pipe manufacturing, which uses the same thermoplastic as composite matrix and liner could create a resistance to external pressure and prevent damage from rapid gas decompression. This also ensures the strongest interface bonding between liners and composites thus providing good mechanical properties of the overall composite structure.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The carbon fibres used in this work were high strength and modulus, unsized but industrially oxidized continuous polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based carbon fibres which was kindly supplied by Hexcel Corporation (HexTow™ AS4 12k, Cambridge, United Kingdom). Polyvinylidene fluoride ($T_m = 165 - 170$ °C) in powder form was kindly supplied by Arkema Inc. (Kynar® 711, King of Prussia, PA, United States). In order to disperse polyvinylidene fluoride powder in water, a surfactant from BASF was used (Cremophor® A 25, Ludwigshafen, Germany). A polyvinylidene fluoride pipe was purchased from Professional Plastics (50 mm schedule 80 x 6 m, Fullerton, United States) and was used as internal liner for the reinforced composite pipe.

2.2 Composite manufacturing

Continuous unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride preregs 12 mm wide and 0.1 mm thick was manufactured using a wet powder impregnation process [7-9]. A schematic diagram of the manufacturing process can be seen in Fig 1. Continuous unsized AS4 carbon fibres were pulled through

an impregnation bath consisting of polyvinylidene fluoride powder slurry in water while maintaining a tension on the fibre creel of 100 g. The tension on the fibre was measured and controlled using a closed loop control unit. The impregnated fibres were then passed through a series of infra-red heated ovens to dry off water and melt the polyvinylidene fluoride onto the fibre tow. The molten polymer impregnated fibres then passed through a series of heated pins to spread the melted polyvinylidene fluoride evenly within the fibre tow. The resulting continuous unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride prepreg was then allowed to consolidate by means of rotating rollers at room temperature while pulled using a haul-off at a speed of 1 m min^{-1} . The fibre volume fraction of the unidirectional prepreg was maintained to be constant at $60 \pm 3\%$ throughout the manufacturing process. The fibre volume fraction was determined using the formula;

$$V_f = \frac{\rho_m W_f}{\rho_f W_m + \rho_m W_f} \times 100\% \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where V_f is the fibre volume fraction of the composite preregs, ρ_m is matrix density, ρ_f is fibre density, W_m is weight of matrix and W_f is weight of 1 m of fibre.

2.3 Fabrication of reinforced thermoplastic pipes

The method chosen for reinforced thermoplastic pipe fabrication was continuous filament winding. Unreinforced 50 mm Schedule 80 polyvinylidene fluoride pipe was mounted onto a steel mandrel. This pipe was used as the internal liner for the composites. The continuous unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride prepreg were secured onto the pipe by means of melting and fusing the matrix and the pipe. A winding angle of $\pm 55^\circ$ was used in the process (Fig 2.). The

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winding speed was set to 25 mm s⁻¹. The winding process was continued until the desired wall thickness of the carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride pipe was achieved. The reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride pipe was then cut into ring sections of 25 mm length using a diamond blade cutter (Diadisc 4200, Mutronic GmbH & Co., Rieden, Germany). The cut surfaces of these specimens were polished (Buehler Ltd., IL, United States of America) using various grades of sandpaper to ensure even and parallel surface finish. To further prepare the specimen for mechanical characterisation, the polish surfaces were cleaned using ethanol (99.9%, VWR, Leicestershire, United Kingdom) and left to dry in a vacuum oven overnight at 45 °C to remove any excess water or solvent.

2.4 Mechanical Characterisation

A. Split Disk Tensile Test

The apparent hoop stress of unreinforced and reinforced thermoplastic pipes was studied using the split-disk tensile test according to ASTM D2290 [10]. According to this standard, only apparent tensile strength is obtained using this method rather than true tensile strength. This is because during the test, the specimen is subjected to a bending moment at the split between the test fixtures. This occurs due to the change in the profile of the ring during the test. Therefore, the test fixtures were designed to minimize the effect of bending moment on the specimens.

The unreinforced and reinforced thermoplastic pipe rings having an outside diameter of 65 mm and length of 25 mm were used in this test. The specimens had no reduced cross-section, as specified in the section 6.2 of ASTM D2290 (Fig 3). The test was carried out at a crosshead speed of 1.25 mm min⁻¹ until failure. The

apparent hoop tensile strength of the specimens was calculated using the formula:

$$\sigma = \frac{P_{MAX}}{(b_1d_1 + b_2d_2)} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where P_{MAX} is the maximum load at failure, b and d are the thickness and length of the specimen, 1 and 2 indicates the midpoint of disks which are located 180° apart on the horizontal axis. The test was repeated five times. The values presented are the average of the five specimens and the errors are calculated from standard deviations.

B. External Loading Properties

The external loading properties of unreinforced and carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride were investigated using parallel plate loading according to ASTM D2412 [11]. This test method allows the determination of pipe stiffness and stiffness factor. A specimen having a width of 25 mm and outside diameter of 65 mm was positioned between two parallel plates in an Instron 5581 (Instron, High Wycombe, Buckinghamshire, UK). The test was carried out by compressing the specimen at a crosshead speed of 12.5 mm min⁻¹, until the internal diameter of the specimen was subjected to 30% deflection, the test was then stopped. The pipe stiffness, PS was determined using the formula;

$$PS = \frac{F^d}{\Delta y} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where F^d is load per unit length at 30% internal diameter deflection and Δy is the change in the inside diameter of the specimen in the load direction. The stiffness factor, SF was calculated using;

$$SF = 0.149r^3 \cdot PS \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where r is the internal radius of the specimen. The percentage of pipe deflection, P was calculated using:

$$P = \frac{\Delta y}{d_i} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where d_i is the initial inside diameter of the ring in mm. The stiffness factor was also determined using:

$$SF = E \cdot I = E \cdot \frac{t^3}{12} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where E is the flexural modulus in GPa and t is the overall wall thickness of the pipe in mm.

2 Results and Discussion

In this study, continuous unidirectional (UD) carbon fibre reinforced PVDF composite tapes were prepared using a laboratory-scale composite production line wet impregnation route. The resulting continuous UD carbon fibre reinforced PVDF prepregs with a fibre volume fraction of $58 \pm 2\%$ were used to fabricate reinforced thermoplastic pipes (RTPs) using continuous filament winding. The winding angle is the major dominating factor influencing the mechanical performance of RTPs [12]. Higher winding angle contributes to higher hoop modulus and, therefore, a pipe can resist higher buckling load when the reinforced thermoplastic pipes are subjected to external pressure. Lower winding angles on the other hand contribute to higher axial strength and modulus [31]. A winding angle of $\pm 55^\circ$ was chosen for this study, as it is widely used and has been established as the optimum winding angle for a tubular section where the hoop-to-axial stress ratio can be as high as 2:1 [13-14]

The methods chosen for characterising the reinforced thermoplastic pipes were hoop tensile

strength determined using a split disk test and compression determined using parallel plate loading tests. The apparent tensile strength of the pure PVDF pipe was determined to be 52.9 ± 0.3 MPa, which is similar to the tensile strength of Kynar[®] 711 PVDF as quoted by the manufacturer as well as previous results [15]. By adding a 3 mm thick layer of $\pm 55^\circ$ carbon fibre reinforced PVDF around the pure PVDF pipe, the apparent hoop tensile strength increased by 8% to 57 ± 1.2 MPa. (See Table 1).

The stiffness factor of the pure PVDF pipe was 39 ± 2.0 $\mu\text{N/m}$. Based on this result, the PVDF flexural modulus can be calculated using equation 6, and was found to be 2.3 GPa. This value is comparable to the Young's modulus of Kynar[®] 711 PVDF material. The stiffness factor of the RTP made with as-received AS4 fibres was found to be identical to that of the pure PVDF pipe (Table 2). It has been reported that the flexural stiffness of RTPs are usually comparable with unreinforced systems [16] and, therefore, the reinforcement does not have any effect on the stiffness factor of the overall structure. Furthermore, it is difficult to calculate the flexural modulus of the structure as it is made of two different materials (pure PVDF liner and carbon fibre reinforced PVDF). During the test, no rupture, cracking, or crazing was observed on any of the specimens even after being compressed by up to 50% of the internal diameter of the pipe.

3 Conclusion

The search for a strong, lightweight material to replace heavy and corrodible alloy pipes used for the exploration of deep-water offshore oil fields has motivated the oil and gas industry over the past few decades. PVDF, a polymer approved by the oil and gas industry to be used as internal liner in offshore pipelines and risers, has yet to be utilised completely. It has been shown previously that it is possible to reinforce

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polyvinylidene fluoride using carbon fibres. In this study, reinforced thermoplastic pipe was fabricated by winding carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride prepregs on a pure polyvinylidene fluoride pipe. The resulting reinforced thermoplastic pipe was subjected to split disk tensile test and compressed between two-parallel plates.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE) Malaysia for bursary for SRS. The authors would also like to thank Mr. Joseph Megyessi (Composite Centre, Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London) for his help with the mechanical tests.

Table 1. Apparent tensile strength of pure polyvinylidene fluoride and carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride pipes

<i>Specimen</i>	<i>Apparent tensile strength (MPa)</i>
Pure PVDF	52.9 ± 0.3
CF/PVDF	57.2 ± 1.2

Table 2 Stiffness factor, E.I of pure polyvinylidene fluoride and carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride pipes

<i>Specimen</i>	<i>Stiffness factor, E·I (μN.m)</i>
Pure PVDF	38.8 ± 0.5
CF/PVDF	38.7 ± 0.3

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing the continuous manufacturing of unidirectional

carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride prepregs.

Figure 2. Helical ±55° wound carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride pipe

Figure 3 Split disk tensile configurations to determine the apparent hoop tensile strength of both unreinforced and carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride pipe rings

Figure 4 External loading using two-parallel plates to determine the stiffness factor of pure polyvinylidene fluoride and carbon fibre reinforced polyvinylidene fluoride pipes

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